

MRI and MR Spectroscopy in Evaluation of Acquired White Matter Diseases: A Prospective Cross-sectional StudyNath A¹, Chakrabartty DK², Pegu BJ³, Kutum T⁴, Islam MI⁵¹Post Graduate Trainee, Department of Radiology, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam²Professor and Head, Department of Radiology, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam^{3,4,5}Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, Silchar Medical College and Hospital, Assam

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim & Objectives:** The aim of this study is to determine the imaging characteristics of acquired white matter diseases on Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Spectroscopy (MRS) and also to determine age and sex distribution of different acquired white matter diseases in patients at Silchar Medical college and Hospital.**Material & Methods:** The main source of data for this study was the patients referred from the Department of Medicine and other departments of Silchar Medical College and Hospital. All Patients referred for radiological evaluation with clinically known or suspected pathologies of various acquired white matter diseases were included in the study. The study was carried out for a period of 1 year from March 1, 2023 to February 29, 2024. MRI evaluation was carried out using SIEMENS TIM AVANTO 1.5T SCANNER. Various conventional and advanced MR pulse sequences with/without contrast was used. MRI and MR Spectroscopy was done in all cases and DWI was done whenever indicated.**Results:** A total of 50 patients with different acquired white matter diseases on MRI were studied over a study period of 1 year. Out of 50 patients, those diagnosed with infections were 23 (46%), vascular causes were 16 (32%), inflammatory causes were 8 (16%) and toxic causes were 3 (6%). Males were more affected in our study (58 %) as compared to females (42 %). Among male patients, the highest number of acquired demyelinating disease were found between 41-50 years age-group and among female patients, most commonly affected age group were 31-40 years. In most of the acquired demyelinating diseases, patchy and asymmetrical involvement of lesions is noted. Periventricular white matter involvement is more commonly seen than subcortical white matter. Almost all acquired demyelinating diseases have “decreased N-acetylaspartate (NAA)” level and “increased choline (Cho)” levels. Lactate peak is observed in acute phases of the demyelinating diseases. “Decreased N-acetylaspartate/Creatine (NAA/Cr) and increased choline/creatine (Cho/Cr) ratio” was noted in all acquired demyelinating diseases.**Conclusions:** The recognition of new mechanisms of disease and recent advances in therapy, with refinements in MRI diagnosis and follow-up, make white matter diseases one of the most rapidly evolving fields of knowledge.**Keywords:** White Matter, Periventricular, Subcortical, Myelination, MR Spectroscopy.

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Introduction

Brain white matter (WM) is crucial for linking different grey matter (GM) areas and transmitting information. As a vital part of the central nervous system, it ensures efficient neural signal transmission across the brain. Primarily made up of myelinated axons, white matter enables communication between gray matter areas, where neuron cell bodies reside, and other parts of the brain and spinal cord. The health and functionality of white matter are essential for cognitive functions, motor skills, and overall neurological well-being. [1] It contains the networks of neurons and axons and connects the different motor and cognitive cortical regions of brain. WM comprises axons (both myelinated and unmyelinated) and glial cells which

includes astrocytes, oligodendrocytes, ependymal cells, choroid plexus cells and microglia. Myelin is electric insulation around axons; it provides fast conduction of nerve impulses and prevents any damage to the nerve fibers. [2] White matter diseases are a broad group of heterogeneous conditions that disrupt the typical pattern of myelination. It encompasses the different congenital and acquired processes. Demyelinating diseases are a subgroup of white matter disorders characterized by destruction or damage of normally myelinated structures. Acquired dysmyelinating diseases are genetically determined white matter disorders characterized by abnormal myelin formation. [3] Demyelinating diseases are further subdivided into

autoimmune, infectious, vascular, and toxic-metabolic categories. Generally, demyelinating diseases are divided into primary and secondary categories according to causation. Primary demyelinating diseases, including multiple sclerosis (MS), are of an unknown etiology, while secondary includes a wide range of conditions with identifiable causes. Whether it be primary or secondary, all demyelinating disorders have something in common: it's the destruction of myelin or oligodendrocytes, the cells that manufacture myelin. [4] Only in the last few decades of the improvement of imaging technology that rigorous research has been conducted on and through which White Matter Diseases have been understood. The diagnosis of a majority of the conditions is by correlating clinical features with MRI findings. Most of the White Matter Diseases are reversible if diagnosed and treated on time, emphasizing prompt and precise diagnosis; this is where neuroimaging comes to play its role. [4]

MRI has played a vital role in the diagnostic work-up of leukoencephalopathy patients. First, MRI is often the modality of choice to document the presence of white matter abnormalities. While occasionally CT scans will show evidence of white matter hypodensity, MRI is vastly superior in both sensitivity and resolution. Second, it has been definitively established that certain leukoencephalopathies consistently manifest distinctive patterns of MRI abnormalities. These are the uniform patterns among the patients with the same disorder and vary between patients having different disorders, making MRI a technique of high diagnostic value in the identification and characterization of such conditions. [5]

Conventional MR imaging is performed based on the signal differences in relaxation properties and the number of free water protons. Although this technique is susceptible to lesions, it has low specificity for pathological tissue characterization and is also limited in quantitative tissue characterization. Advanced MR imaging has developed several techniques that increase diagnostic power. The fluid-attenuated inversion recovery sequence (FLAIR) is much more sensitive than standard proton density and T2-weighted images for showing periventricular white matter lesions. DWI is beneficial in showing an ischemic or demyelinating process that may mimic an infective or malignant lesion since it will show restricted diffusion inside the brain. [6]

MR spectroscopy is the primary method used for the biochemical evaluation of intracranial pathology, acquired white matter diseases included. Through this process, the presence and relative quantities of different chemical metabolites are determined within the brain. MRS becomes a valuable helpful tool in further evaluating a host of other intracranial conditions. This technique is beneficial in accurately identifying the primary category of disease

underlying observed lesions, such as neoplastic, infective, inflammatory, or ischemic origins.[7]

This study was chosen for the acquired disease of white matter and the role that MR imaging performs in this context. Therefore, the present study will explore the imaging characteristics of acquired diffuse white matter diseases, with further evaluation of the role of MRS in the characterization of the disease process.

Aims and Objectives

The aims and objectives of this study:

1. To determine the imaging characteristics of acquired white matter diseases on Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Spectroscopy (MRS).
2. To determine age and sex distribution of different acquired white matter diseases.

Material & Methods

The main source of data for this study was the patients referred from the Department of Medicine and other departments of Silchar Medical College and Hospital. All Patients referred for radiological evaluation with clinically known or suspected pathologies of various acquired white matter diseases were included in the study. The study was carried out for a period of 1 year from March 1, 2023 to February 29, 2024. It is a prospective cross-sectional observational study. MRI evaluation was carried out using SIEMENS TIM AVANTO 1.5T SCANNER. Various conventional and advanced MR pulse sequences with/without contrast was used. MRI and MR Spectroscopy was done in all cases and DWI was done whenever indicated.

The sample size was calculated by using the following "Danial sample size formula:

$N = \{Z^2 \times p(1-p)/d^2\}$, N= Sample size, Z= Statistics for a level of confidence (For the level of confidence of 95%, which is convention, Z Value is 1.96), p= expected prevalence or proportion (Prevalence of Acquired white matter diseases in Silchar Medical College & Hospital= 15 %). d = precision (d is considered 10 % to produce good precision and smaller error of estimate)". My sample size included 50 patients.

Patients referred for radiological evaluation with clinically known or suspected pathologies of various acquired white matter diseases were included in our study. Exclusion criteria included a) Patients with inherited white matter diseases, b) Patients with brain neoplasm, c) Patients with contraindications to MRI, e.g., presence of pacemaker, severe claustrophobia and d) Inability to give informed consent. After taking a brief clinical history and performing a detailed clinical examination, the patient was put for MR Imaging in the MR Section of the Department of Radiology, Silchar Medical College & Hospital.

Before the scans were performed, history of any metallic implant into the body was enquired from the patient or attendants & the procedure was explained in their mother tongue to the patient so as to allay any apprehensions. An informed consent was taken from the patient as well as the attendant. The patient was asked to have nothing orally for at least 4 hours preceding the scan. Axial, coronal and sagittal spin-echo (SE) T1W and T2W, FLAIR and MRS were obtained in all patients. DWI, ADC and contrast MR sequences” were performed in selected cases.

Results and Observation

In the present study comprising of 50 patients, those diagnosed with infections were 23 (46%), those with vascular causes were 16 (32%), those diagnosed with inflammatory causes were 8 (16%) and with toxic causes were 3 (6%).

Small vessel disease (22 %) was the commonest acquired white matter disease in our study, followed

by Acute Disseminated Encephalomyelitis aka. ADEM (18 %) and Herpes Simplex Virus Encephalitis (14 %).

The highest percentage of cases were found in the age group 41-50 years (38%) followed by the age group of 31-40 years (34 %) and the age group of 11-20 years (14%) and 21-30 years (6%). Lowest percentage of cases was found in the age group of 0-10 years (4%) and 51-60 years (4%).

Males were more affected in our study (58 %) as compared to females (42 %). Male to female ratio was 1.38: 1.

Female predominance was observed in Multiple sclerosis (MS), followed by Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMO). However, rest of the acquired demyelinating diseases showed male preponderance.

Figure 1: Distribution of cases according to final diagnosis [n=50]

Figure 2: Spectrum of acquired white matter diseases in our study

Figure 3: Sex distribution of total cases

Figure 4: Age (in years) distribution of cases

Figure 5: Sex distribution of individual cases

Figure 6: Distribution of Age group and sex of patients

Among male patients, the highest number of acquired demyelinating disease was found between 41-50 years age-group, followed by 31-40 years. Among female patients, most commonly affected age group were 31-40 years followed by 41-50 years.

Table 1: Conventional MR imaging findings in different cases according to distribution characteristics of lesions (n=50)

Lesions (Final diagnosis)	Sym-met-ri-cal	Asym-met-ri-cal	Pate-hy	Dif-fuse	perive-ntric-ular	sub-corti-cal	Gray matter		lesion load (no. of le-sion>1 cm)
							Inv	Not Inv	
Multiple Sclerosis	-	03	03	-	03	01	-	03	02
Neuromyelitis Optica (NMO)	04	01	05	-	03	-	-	05	-
ADEM	01	08	07	02	04	05	05	04	-
HSV Encephalitis	-	07	05	02	03	04	04	03	-
HIV Encephalitis	04	-	04	-	04	-	-	04	-
PMLE	-	02	02	-	01	02	-	02	-
SSPE	-	01	-	01	01	01	-	01	-
SVIC	-	11	07	04	11	-	-	11	-
PRES	05	-	01	04	02	03	-	05	-
Acute alcohol intoxication	-	01	-	01	01	-	01	-	-
Marchiafava-Bignami Disease	02	-	01	01	02	-	-	02	-
Total	16	34	35	15	35	16	10	40	02

Acquired white matter diseases were noted most commonly involving the cerebral lobes and the corpus callosum. Few of the cases showed involvement of ganglio-thalamic region, internal capsule, brainstem, cerebellum and spinal cord.

Corpus callosum is most commonly involved in Multiple Sclerosis (MS), followed by Marchiafava-Bignami disease (MBD). Spinal cord involvement is seen in Multiple Sclerosis (MS), Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMO) and Acute Disseminated Encephalomyelitis (ADEM). In most of the acquired demyelinating diseases, patchy and asymmetrical involvement of lesions is noted. Posterior reversible leukoencephalopathy (PRES)

showed diffuse and symmetrical involvement. HIV encephalitis showed patchy but asymmetric involvement. Gray matter is usually spared except in ADEM, HSV encephalitis and acute alcohol intoxication. Periventricular white matter involvement is more commonly seen than subcortical white matter. Multiple Sclerosis (MS) showed short segment transverse myelitis (STM) with unilateral involvement of optic nerve.

However, NMO showed long segment transverse myelitis (LETM) with 60 % (3/5) cases showing involvement of bilateral optic nerve. ADEM showed long segment transverse myelitis (LETM). Only acute cases of MS, ADEM and Herpes simplex virus

(HSV) encephalitis shows restrictive diffusion. Acute toxic demyelination showed restrictive diffusion. On MR Spectroscopy, almost all acquired demyelinating diseases have decreased N-acetylaspartate (NAA) level and increased choline

(Cho) levels. Lactate peak is observed in acute phases of the demyelinating diseases. Decreased N-acetylaspartate/Creatine (NAA/Cr) and increased choline/creatine (Cho/Cr) ratio was noted in all acquired demyelinating diseases.

Table 2: Conventional MR imaging findings in different cases according to involvement of spinal cord and optic nerve (n=50)

	Spinal	Cord	Optic	Nerve
Lesions (Final diagnosis)	STM	LETM	U/L	B/L
Multiple Sclerosis (n=3)	03	-	02	-
Neuromyelitis Optica (NMO) (n=5)	-	05	02	03
ADEM (n=9)	-	06	-	-
HSV Encephalitis (n=7)	-	-	-	-
HIV Encephalitis (n=4)	-	-	-	-
PMLE (n=2)	-	-	-	-
SSPE (n=1)	-	-	-	-
SVIC(n=11)	-	-	-	-
PRES(n=5)	-	-	-	-
Acute alcohol intoxication (n=1)	-	-	-	-
Marchiafava-Bignami Disease (n=2)	-	-	-	-
Total	03	11	04	03

Table 3: MR spectroscopy (at TE=135ms) finding in different lesions (n=50)

Lesions (Final diagnosis)	NAA		Cho		ml		Lactate		NAA/Cr		Cho/Cr	
	N/Inc	Dec	Inc	Dec	Pr mm	Abs	Pr ww	Abs	Inc	Dec	Inc	Dec
Multiple Sclerosis	1	2	3	-	-	3	1	2	-	2	3	-
Neuromyelitis Optica (NMO)	4	1	1	-	-	5	-	5	-	-	11	-
ADEM	4	5	6	-	-	9	3	6	-	5	6	-
HSV Encephalitis	4	3	3	-	-	7	3	4	-	3	3	-
HIV Encephalitis	1	3	3	-	-	-	413	-	-	33	-	-
PMLE	-	22	-	-	-	2	-	2	-	22	-	-
SSPE	-	1	1	-	-	1	-	1	-	1	1	-
SVIC	8	3	3	-	-	11	-	11	-	3	3	-
PRES	3	2	2	-	-	5	2	3	-	22	-	-
Acute alcohol intoxication	-	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	1	-
Marchiafava-Bignami Disease	1	1	1	-	-	2	-	2	-	11	-	-

Discussion

The term acquired white matter disorders consists of demyelinating disorders that exhibit quite a different pattern of white matter abnormalities from those observed among the hereditary dysmyelinating disorders. Our study group comprised of 50 patients of both sexes from 0 to 60 years. Majority of our cases were among the age group 31-50 years which comprised 72% of all cases.

In the present study comprising of 50 patients, those diagnosed with infections were 23 (46%), those with

vascular causes were 16 (32%), those diagnosed with inflammatory causes were 8 (16%) and with toxic causes were 3 (6%). The findings of our study are comparable to the studies by Randa O. Kaddah. et al and Mohsen E. et al (2015). [8] Almost a similar pattern of distribution was also found in a study conducted by Van der Knaap et al in 1991, in which he evaluated 277 patients over a period of 4 years and found acquired demyelinating disorders as 75% of the total white matter disorders. However, in his study, MS was the most common demyelinating disease which comprised 25% of all white matter

diseases. [9] In our present study, out of the total 50 patients, male constituted about 29 (58%) and females about 21 (42%). Among the 29 male patients, the median age-group was 45.92 and among 21 female patients, the median age was 34.5. The findings of our study are comparable to the studies by Randa O. Kaddah. et al. (2015).[8]

Multiple Sclerosis

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is an inflammatory demyelinating disease of CNS of unknown origin. It was observed in our study that MS is most commonly seen in 3rd to 4th decade of life with slight female preponderance. Most of the patients (67%) were in the age group of 31-40 years. These findings of age distribution and of female preponderance are in agreement with geographically based study by Weinschenker et al in 1989. [10]

The striking abnormality noticed in our study on conventional MR imaging was that all MS patients had bilateral multifocal asymmetrical lesions, hyperintense on T2. These lesions were small and isolated, sometime ovoid and large (more than 10mm in two out of three cases) and isolated but rarely highly confluent seen only in one case.

These T2 hyperintense lesion load did not correlate with the clinical manifestation as only one out of three patients were clinically sick and had severe symptoms. Our findings are in concurrence with the study conducted by Miki et al in 1999 [11], whereby it was found that there was no significant correlation between T2 lesion volume and standardized disability measurements despite a substantial increase in the T2 lesion volume over time. Patients have an increase in total T2 lesion volume in the brain irrespective of their clinical status or disability measurement.

On contrast enhanced study on three patients, one showed contrast enhancement that correlated with the clinical worsening. Barkhof et al in 1992 [12] reported similar correlation of enhancing lesions with clinical symptoms. He found that clinical worsening is associated with increased frequency of Gado- enhancing lesions and is a marker of disruption of the blood brain barrier.

The distributions of the lesions were predominantly periventricular and deep white matter as seen in 100% cases in our study. But subcortical U fibers were seen to be involved in only 33 % in our patients. None of the cases was found with isolated subcortical U fibers involvement. The corpus callosum was the most frequent site of involvement seen in 100% of our cases. Similar orientation of lesions were reported by Horowitz et al 1989 [13] where more than 85% of MS patients had ovoid periventricular lesions oriented perpendicular to the long axis of the brain and lateral ventricles.

Diffusion weighted imaging was done in all 3 patients. It was observed that two out three(67%) patients showed facilitated diffusion pattern (increase in ADC) seen as decrease in hyperintensity with increasing 'b' values and hyperintense on ADC maps. Facilitated diffusion in acute and active demyelination is due to axonal damage and vasogenic edema. Verhoye et al in 1997 [14] and Trapp et al in 1998 [15] also reported similar findings in their studies. Increase in ADC was also noted in chronic MS plaques, where in the increase is due to continued myelin destruction and loss of structural integrity. Werring et al in 1999 [16] also found similar increase in ADC in chronic demyelination.

Only one out of three (33%) patients showed restricted diffusion (reduction of ADC) seen as increase in hyperintensity with increasing 'b' values and hypointense on ADC maps. This may be due to myelin sheath swelling, dense inflammatory infiltrates with consequent reduction in extracellular space or due to cytotoxic edema. Pagani et al in 1999 [17] and Rovira et al in 2002 [18] found similar findings in their study.

On proton-MRS (TE=135ms) various cerebral metabolites were studied and it was observed that N-acetyl aspartate (NAA), choline (Cho) and creatine (Cr) were the 3 major peaks noted in all cases. At TE=30ms, myoinositol (mI) peak was noted in two patients. On comparing peak ratios with respect to Cr, it was observed that NAA/Cr was reduced in 67% of our cases and was near normal in 33%cases. Cho/Cr was increased in all the 3 cases. The lowest level of NAA/Cr was noted in 2 cases. These cases were in acute stage of demyelination and Cho/Cr ratio was found maximum in the same cases. Out of these 2 cases, 1 showed lactate peak contributing to the process of acute demyelination. Reduction in NAA peak suggested neuronal damage. The choline peak signified increased level of substrate needed for membrane turnover and myelin formation.

Our findings of MRS are in agreement with that of Chen et al in 2001 [19] who conducted serial proton MRS for better understanding of biochemical changes within MS lesions. He found a decrease in NAA/Cr and an increase in Cho/Cr in all spectra. He also suggested that lowest level of NAA/Cr and highest level of Cho/Cr with lactate peak corresponded to early stage of disease.

Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorder

In our study, it was observed most commonly between 31-50 years age-group with a slight female preponderance (male: female ratio= 3:2). The findings are similar to the study conducted by Sarbu et al. in 2016 [20] and by Cao et al in 2020. [21]

On conventional MR imaging, 3 out of 5 (60%) patients showed periventricular white matter signal

hyperintensity on T2-weighted image. However, subcortical involvement was not seen in any of the cases. These findings were in agreement with the study conducted by Cao et al in 2020 (21). According to his study, 40% patients had non-specific white matter changes, 36.3% had normal MRI findings, 17.7% had specific periependymal and dorsal brainstem lesions, while 6% had MS-like lesions.

All five cases of NMO showed long segment transverse myelitis and three (60%) out of five patients had bilateral involvement of optic nerve. While the remaining two (40%) patients showed unilateral involvement of optic nerve. Our study is in agreement with Lotze et al (2008) [22] who studied 9 female patients with neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders. Among these patients, 8 had both transverse myelitis and optic neuritis, while 1 had longitudinally extensive transverse myelitis without optic neuritis.

On proton-MRS (TE=135ms) various cerebral metabolites were studied and it was observed that only one out of five (20%) patient showed decreased NAA peak and increased choline peak with decreased NAA/Cr and increased Cho/Cr ratios. However, remaining 80% patients showed normal NAA and Cho levels. The findings are similar to the study conducted by De Seze et al in 2009. [23]

Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM)

Our study included 9 ADEM cases, out of which six (67%) were male and three (33%) were females. The common age group affected in our study was 11-20 years (67%), followed by 0-10 years (22%).

In our study it was observed that, in contrast to MS, the lesions were larger in most of the cases and sometimes even highly confluent. Subcortical white matter was more commonly involved as seen in 56% of the all ADEM cases unlike MS (33%).

Periventricular white matter was involved in only 44% of the cases. In contrast to the situation in MS, the cortical gray matter was involved relatively frequently as seen in 56% of our cases in ADEM. Corpus callosum and spinal cord was involved in less number of cases. Similar distributions of ADEM lesions were noted by Menor et al in 1997 [24] and by Caldemeyer et al in 1991. [25]

In our study, long segment transverse myelitis was noted on MR imaging of spine in six (67%) out of nine patients. This finding was similar to the study conducted by Steiner et al. in 2003 [26].

All our ADEM cases were further studied by diffusion-weighted imaging. It was observed that there was increased hyperintensity with increasing "b" values in 4 cases out of 9(44%) that appeared hypointense on ADC maps (restrictive pattern) suggesting either acute inflammatory and

demyelinating process. 5 out of 9 cases (56%) showed increase in hypointensity with increasing 'b' values and hyperintense on ADC maps. This may be due to total myelin destruction and gliosis representing chronic demyelinating process.

On proton MRS, we found reduced NAA/Cr ratio in five out of all nine cases and near normal levels of NAA/Cr ratio in rest of the 4 cases. Lowest level of NAA/Cr ratio was seen in 3 cases out of which 1 showed restrictive pattern on diffusion, confirming acute demyelination.

Six out of nine (67%) cases showed increased Cho/Cr ratios and the highest level that was seen in 1 case also showed restrictive pattern on diffusion and the same case showed lactate peak suggesting acute demyelination. Similar results of reduced NAA/Cr and increase Cho/Cr was also shown by Bizzi et al in 2001 [27], in his study on the imaging characteristics in ADEM. However, he stressed that on follow up MRI and MRSI, abnormalities fully resolved. Harada et al in 2000 [28] also found lactate peak in 2 different cases of ADEM showing acute demyelination.

Herpes Simplex Encephalitis

Our study had 7 cases of Herpes simplex encephalitis. 57.1% cases were young men in the 3rd and 4th decade of their life who had presented with rapid onset of impaired consciousness, fever and seizures, while 42% were women in the 2nd and 3rd decade of their life.

MR study revealed similar findings in all seven cases. The findings included low signal intensity on T1 W and high signal intensity on T2W images. The lesions were localized to bilateral temporal lobes and insular cortex with associated gyral swelling. However, only one patient showed involvement of bilateral subfrontal lobes. These features resembled the findings of Daemerel et al., (1992) [29] and Tien et al., (1993). [30] Five out of seven (71.4%) patients had restricted diffusion in the involved areas on DWI. Daemerel et al., (1999) [31] had described restricted diffusion in the involved areas in a case of viral encephalitis.

On proton-MR spectroscopy, three out of seven (43%) patients showed a reduction in NAA/Cr ratio and an increase in Cho/Cr ratio. Lactate peak was also noted in these three patients. These studies were in agreement with the studies conducted by Daemerel et al. in 1992 [29] and Takanashi et al. in 1997. [32]

HIV encephalitis

Our study included 4 cases of HIV encephalitis who had positive history of HIV and were clinically sick with altered sensorium. All four cases were young men in the 3rd and 4th decade of their life who had

presented with rapid onset of impaired consciousness, fever and seizures.

The MR findings revealed bilateral symmetrical hyperintense lesions involving periventricular and lobar white matter and deep gray matter with sparing of overlying subcortical U fibers and cortex. Cerebral atrophy was noticed and was bilaterally symmetrical. Similar MR findings were observed in the studies conducted by Thumber et al in 1997 [33] and Berger et al in 2000. [34] In our study, on proton MRS (at TE=135ms), we found reduced NAA/Cr ratios and increased Cho/Cr ratio in the regions of white matter signal abnormality in three (75%) out of four patients. MRS findings in our study were similar to that of Simone et al in 1998 [35] and Barkar et al in 1995 [36]. Pavlakis et al in 1998 [37] emphasized that the decrease level of NAA/Cr in cases of HIV encephalitis improved after antiretroviral therapy and MRS helped in monitoring the treatment and response to therapy.

However, MR spectroscopic study done at TE=30ms, showed myo-inositol peaks (mI) in only two (50%) patients. These were in correlation with the study conducted by Lopez-Villegas et al in 2000. [38]

Progressive multifocal leukoencephalopathy

Only two cases of progressive multifocal leukoencephalopathy (PML) were included in our study. Both cases were young men in the 3rd and 4th decade of their life who had presented with rapid onset of impaired consciousness.

The imaging findings in our cases were multifocal hyperintense lesions on T2W images, asymmetrically involving cerebral hemisphere. The lesions involved subcortical white matter with relative sparing of periventricular white matter in one out of two cases. These types of distribution of lesions were unlike that seen in HIV encephalopathy in our study. Similar MR findings were reported by Berger et al in 1998 [39] and Levy et al in 1996 [40].

MRS in our case revealed markedly decreased in NAA/Cr ratio and elevated Cho levels. The severity of NAA reduction signified severe neuronal and axonal loss and these matched with the clinical severity of our case. Semone et al in 1998 [35] also resulted in his study that significant decrease in NAA/Cr level was present in all HIV positive cases and in PML; NAA/Cr was significantly lower than HIV encephalitis.

Similar findings of brain atrophy, asymmetric white matter lesions with marked decrease in NAA/Cr ratio and marked increase in Cho/Cr ratio was also reported by Laubenberger et al in 1996 [41]

Subacute Sclerosing Panencephalitis

Only one case of subacute sclerosing panencephalitis (SSPE) was included in our study. It was

noted in the age-group of 11-20 years and was a male patient who presented with altered sensorium and had a previous history of measles 9 years back.

The MR findings revealed hyperintense signal intensities on T2 weighted images in the subcortical and periventricular white matter involving bilateral frontal and temporal lobes with associated cerebral atrophy. The findings of our study are comparable to the studies conducted by Tuncay et al in 1996 (42). Similar high signal lesions involving subcortical and periventricular white matter was also noted in the study by Anlar et al. in 1996 [43].

On proton MR spectroscopy, our case showed reduced levels of NAA/Cr ratio and increased Cho/Cr ratio, suggesting neuronal loss and demyelination. The findings are in agreement with the study conducted by Alkan et al in 2003 [44]

Small Vessel Disease

Our study included 11 cases of small vessel disease (SVD). Most (90%) of the cases were in the age group 41-60 years with a male predominance (male: female ratio= 1.2:1). The findings of our study are comparable to the studies by Fazekas et al. in 1993 [45].

The imaging findings in our cases were irregular, asymmetrical periventricular and confluent deep white matter hyperintensities on T2W images, suggesting severe ischemic tissue damage resulting from mild perivascular changes to significant arteriolosclerosis. These findings were in agreement with the studies conducted by Fazekas et al. in 1993 [45] and Zhao et al. in 2020 [46].

On MR spectroscopic study, three (27.3%) out of eleven cases showed reduced levels of NAA/Cr ratio and increased levels of Cho/Cr ratio. However, remaining eight (73%) of them showed normal levels of NAA/Cr and Cho/Cr ratios. Nitkunan et al. in 2008 [47] in his study also found significant decrease in NAA/Cr ratio and increase in Cho/Cr ratio in symptomatic SVD patients compared to hypertensive and normotensive groups.

Posterior Reversible Encephalopathy Syndrome

Our study included 5 cases of posterior reversible encephalopathy syndrome (PRES). Out of total five cases, four (80%) were female and one (20%) was male. Hinchey et al in 1996 [48], conducted a study on 15 patients (13 female and 2 male) with PRES who had characteristic clinical and imaging features of this syndrome.

It was observed that four (80%) out of five cases showed diffuse and symmetrical involvement of bilateral parieto-occipital lobes. Three (60%) patients showed involvement of subcortical white matter, while periventricular involvement was also noted in two (40%) patients. The findings of our

study are comparable to the studies by Kwon et al. in 2001 [49].

The imaging findings in our study showed symmetric high signal intensities on T2 weighted images in the periventricular and subcortical white matter of bilateral parieto-occipital lobes. This was in agreement with the study conducted by Yuan et al. in 2016 [50]. On proton MR spectroscopy, our study revealed significant reduction in NAA/Cr ratio, suggesting neuronal dysfunction or loss and an increase in Cho/Cr ratio in two (40%) out of five cases. Remaining three (60%) patients showed normal levels of N-acetylaspartate (NAA) and Choline (Cho). Two (40%) patients also showed high lactate peak indicating acute phase. These findings were similar with the studies conducted by Lee et al. in 2009 [51], Yuan et al. in 2016 [50] and Sheikh et al. in 2020 [52].

Acute Alcohol Intoxication

In our study group we had 1 patient who was diagnosed with acute alcohol intoxication in the age group 31-40 years. On conventional MR imaging, the patient with acute alcoholic intoxication had bilaterally, asymmetrical, patchy hyperintense lesions on long TR images mostly involving periventricular and deep white matter. Cortical grey matter of bilateral frontal and parietal lobes were also involved. Van der knaap et al in 1992 [53] also emphasized the same findings of alcohol that tends to affect specific vulnerable regions of brain.

It was also observed in our study that the patient showed restrictive pattern on diffusion imaging. This signified acute toxin induced demyelination. Diffusion weighted imaging thus showed an increased sensitivity in the detection of hyperacute stage of demyelination. Heide et al in 1993 [54], in

his study emphasized that DWI revealed white matter lesions much earlier than spin echo imaging. In our study, on MR spectroscopy, we observed the non-specific findings of reduced NAA/Cr and elevated Cho/Cr ratios in the same patient of alcoholic intoxication.

The striking observation that we noticed was the presence of lactate peak that was seen only in alcoholic intoxication. Lactate is not normally present in the brain tissue and detection of a lactate peak is a reflection of anaerobic glycolysis, which was caused by alcohol intoxication. Van der knaap et al in 1992 [53], while evaluating various toxic encephalopathies also noted similar finding along with many other specific metabolites and degradation products.

Marchiafava-Bignami Disease

Two cases of Marchiafava-Bignami disease (MBD) were included in our study. Out of which both were male patients. On MR imaging, MBD patients showed a characteristic involvement of the middle layers of corpus callosum, which appeared hypointense on T1-weighted images and hyperintense on T2-weighted images, suggesting demyelination and necrosis resulting from chronic alcoholism. Surrounding periventricular white matter involving bilateral frontal lobes also showed hyperintense signal on T2-weighted images. Corpus callosal atrophy was also noted. These findings were in accordance with the study conducted by Kohler et al. in 2000 [55] and Murthy et al. in 2014 [56]. In our study, the spectroscopic findings revealed decrease in NAA/Cr ratio and an increase in Cho/Cr ratio in one (50%) out of two patients. This was in agreement with the study conducted by Gambini et al. in 2003 [57].

CASE 1: Multiple Sclerosis

T2/FLAIR sagittal (A) & (B) showing multiple round to oval hyperintense plaques distributed randomly involving subcortical, periventricular and juxta cortical white matter.

Figure 7:

E) MRS TE = 30 ms

F) MRS TE = 135 ms

On MR Spectroscopy, at TE=30ms (E), myo-inositol peak is noted. At TE =135ms (F), decreased NAA peak and increased Cho peak is noted.

Figure 8:

Figure 9:

CASE 2: Neuromyelitis Optica Spectrum Disorder

Figure 10:

C) MRS TE = 135 ms

On MR Spectroscopy, at TE = 135ms (C), decreased NAA peak and increased Cho peak is noted.

Figure 11:

D) T2 Sagittal Dorsal Spine

E) Coronal T2/FLAIR

T2 Sagittal DL spine (D) shows long segment involvement with corresponding hyperintense signal intensity. Coronal T2WI (E) shows hyperintensity involving the right optic nerve, suggesting optic neuritis.

Figure 12:

CASE 3: Acute Disseminated Encephalomyelitis (ADEM)

A) T2W Axial

B) FLAIR Axial

Axial T2W (A) and axial FLAIR (B) images show bilateral but asymmetric patchy areas of hyperintense lesions, involving the deep gray matter nuclei and periventricular-subcortical white matter.

Figure 13:

C) MRS TE = 135 ms

On MR Spectroscopy, at TE =135ms (C), decreased NAA peak, increased Cho peak and lactate peak is noted.

D) T2 Sagittal Cervical Spine

E) STIR Sagittal Cervical Spine

Sagittal T2-weighted image (D) and STIR image (E) of cervical spine shows long segment involvement with corresponding hyperintense signal intensity.

Figure 14:

Conclusion

The clinical features are fairly non-specific for the various acquired white matter diseases. MR imaging especially the newer techniques like diffusion imaging and MR spectroscopy when combined with conventional MR imaging helps us in arriving at an early and accurate diagnosis. MR spectroscopy can help in the early diagnosis of disease, assessment of disease activity i.e. in differentiating acute from chronic stages of the disease process and in monitoring the disease progress and therapy. The changes in magnetic resonance spectroscopy correlate well with the functional and clinical stages of disease and its histopathological findings.

Thus, magnetic resonance spectroscopy are invaluable tools when combined with conventional MR imaging in the early and accurate diagnosis, characterization of diffuse white matter diseases and monitoring the disease progress and therapy in an appropriate clinical setting. With all its advantages, MR is still beyond the reach of an overwhelming part of the population, particularly in a country like India.

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